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UNVEILING THE PROCESS OF CROSS-CULTURAL DESIGN: MAKING THE IMPLICIT EXPLICIT.

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ABSTRACT

Dynamics of globalization and cultural diversity have enriched our world. Thus, new conditions for the practice of design have emerged and the number of designers designing for cultures other than their own has increased. This study aims to understand the effect of difference between designers' and users' cultural backgrounds on the design process as well as the challenges and opportunities created by this difference. Grounded theory was employed as the methodological framework. Data were collected from interviewing ten geographically dispersed designers who have experience in cross-cultural design processes. Results emerged from three levels of coding and reflective journaling.

Key Words: culture, design, process

INTRODUCTION

New conditions related to the practice of design have emerged with the opposing dynamic of globalization; diversity in unity. Globalization has enriched and diversified lifestyles of people, and cultural diversity in the world has become more visible. With the onset of worldwide product marketing, the design process has become multi-cultural, bringing together designers, users and other stakeholders with different cultural backgrounds. New "non-Western" markets with diverse traditional cultural backgrounds such as China and India have emerged. Entrance into these markets especially by Western entrepreneurs requires cultural competence (Lonner & Hayes, 2004). These emerging conditions have created new responsibilities for designers, such as being able to design in different socio-cultural contexts, and understand and embed cultural factors in product design.

In this study, culture is considered from a national perspective, as a social phenomenon composed of explicit and implicit symbolic forms stemming from religion, traditions, values and norms. When the designer's cultural background is the same as the user, integration of cultural factors in design happens as tacit knowledge. Designing for another culture has the challenge of making explicit what has been implicit within one's own culture.

The objective of this research is to understand the effect of cultural difference between designer and user on the design process. The study especially focuses on the challenges created by the cross-cultural context in product design processes and presents a framework for a "culture-centered design process" that is based on interview results. Three major research questions guided this study:

- 1) What are the major challenges of designing for other cultures?
- 2) What are the major methods used for overcoming the challenges of designing for other cultures?
- 3) How does the process of designing for other cultures differ from a generic user-centered design process?

This research attempts to understand the difference between the generic user-centered design process and the design process where designers and users originate from different cultural backgrounds. The study does not suggest that design processes which take place in cross-cultural contexts need to incorporate cultural aspects in design at all times.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term culture has been defined in various ways in different fields. According to one of the earliest definitions by anthropologist Edward Tylor (1871) culture is a "complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, law, morals, custom, and any

other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society (p.1)”. Spradley and McCurdy (1987) defined culture as composed of mentifacts, sociofacts and artifacts. Mentifacts are about what people know and think including ideals, values and norms. Sociofacts are about how people should behave. Artifacts are what people create in a culture. Thus, culture manifests itself both in visible ways such as artifacts and less-visible ways such as behaviors and norms.

The Iceberg model of culture by French and Bell (1979) defined culture as composed of an explicit, clearly visible top layer, and an implicit, invisible bottom layer. The top layer of culture refers to symbols like artifacts, and written rules, behaviors and rituals. The bottom layer, which is much larger than the visible layer is composed of norms, values, habits, beliefs, and customs. Similarly, Hofstede (1991) uses the onion metaphor to illustrate culture in a model composed of several layers from core to the periphery as values, ritual, heroes, and symbols. According to this view, culture is like an onion that can be peeled, layer by layer, to reveal the content. The definitions of culture introduced above are synthesized into an integrative visual model from which a working definition of culture is developed for this study (Figure 1). For this research, culture is defined as a dynamic body of knowledge embedded in visible forms such as arts and artifacts, observable facts and behaviors such as rituals, language, religion and folklore, and not directly observable, implicit beliefs and values that are shared, adapted and integrated by a social group of people over time.

Figure 1. A visual synthesis of the definitions of culture as a working definition for this study.

The relationship between design and culture has been approached from different perspectives in the Design field. Studies related to culture in design can

be categorized into three general areas; 1. cultural guidelines for the design process, 2. cultural inspiration for design, 3. cross-cultural comparison of user and designer behavior.

In the first category, existing frameworks such as Hofstede’s (1991) cultural dimensions of individualism and collectivism are used as guidelines to understand users in a cross-cultural design context. These studies are helpful for systematic analysis of cultural backgrounds of users. However, they are limited in addressing cultural aspects related to design which are not measurable or classifiable by using guidelines.

For example, Röse (2004) developed a cultural model that can guide user-centered design processes based on cultural characteristics (Hofstede, 1991; Hampden-Turner & Trompenaars, 1997). User factors that can affect the design process were classified into objective (gender, age, ethnicity, etc.) and subjective factors (values, beliefs, rituals, etc.). Cultural data were divided into two categories as cultural mentalities and cultural environments. Cultural mentalities refer to facets within a cultural group’s thought and behavior such as aesthetics, language, learning habits and unconscious rules. Cultural environments refer to cultural facets around thoughts and behaviors such as technical development, educational system, physical environment, law and commercial system. Shen, Wooley and Prior (2006) developed a guideline which can be applied to the design process in Human Computer Interaction. The guideline was a dual layer design filter tool which consisted of designer’s and user’s filters to investigate the selected target group. The designer’s filter referred to the design of the interface based on designer’s particular socio-cultural background, the technology, ergonomics and design factors. The user’s filter represented users who observe the interface through their own cultural filter.

In the second category, studies mostly focus on the visceral level of design and encourage employing cultural elements as an inspiration for visual characteristics of products such as colors and forms. Lin (2007) established a cross-cultural model to transfer features from a cultural object into design elements. The framework consisted of the phases of extracting cultural features from an original cultural

object, transforming these features into design information and design elements and, designing the cultural product. This framework was then applied to product development using Aboriginal clothing culture as the cultural inspiration source.

Moalosi, Popovic and Hudson (2007) developed a framework to consciously integrate cultural aspects into a new product development process. Authors identified a list of socio-cultural factors by content analysis of Botswana's folktales and national culture. This list was presented to design students and they were asked to transform these factors into design features. A culture-oriented design model was proposed by analyzing the feedback of students to the given design task. The framework consisted of three phases: 1. identification of socio-cultural factors through folktales, oral traditions, etc. 2. integration phase where designers interact with users to integrate socio-cultural factors into culturally acceptable products with functional features 3. cherishable culturally oriented products phase where design ideas are linked to users' culture.

In the third category, user's design preferences and designers' approaches to design are compared across cultures. Christiaans and Diehl (2007) did a cross-cultural comparison of design and usability preferences of Dutch and Korean users. A computer based simulation allowed users to design the interface for a microwave. Dutch and Korean users were analyzed by looking at how they displayed the arrangement of buttons on the interface. Korean users focused on functionality of the display while Dutch users preferred aesthetics and functionality together.

According to Tomico, Karapanos, Levy, Mizutani and Yamanaka (2009) individuals' perceptions of products are carriers of implicit cultural insight. This approach was applied to a case study that examined how Japanese pens were perceived by Japanese and Dutch designers with the aim of understanding cross-cultural differences between product attribute prioritization of Japanese and Dutch designers. The results of the study showed that Japanese designers were more concerned with the pragmatic aspects of utility, comfort and visual aesthetics, and Dutch designers were more concerned with durability, symbolic qualities.

As laid out in the literature review, research is missing about the process of designing for another culture that is grounded in field experiences of designers and focused on practical application. This research will fill a gap by exploring the stages and challenges of design processes where the designer and user originate from different cultural backgrounds.

METHODS

Grounded theory (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) is adopted as the methodological framework for this study. Grounded theory was originally developed in the Sociology domain to generate or discover an analytical schema of a process by systematic data analysis through a constant comparative coding. The process is complex and iterative where results are grounded in the data from interview of participants who have experienced a particular process (Strauss & Corbin, 1990).

In this study the data are collected through in-depth interviews. Prior to actual data collection, a pilot study which included seven interviews with a diverse range of designers was conducted to develop the research design. As a result, open-ended interview questions and probes that encouraged story telling about specific examples of cross-cultural design experience were generated. The interview questions were categorized under three different headings; 1) background information about the designer, 2) experiences of the designer when designing for other cultures (including processes, challenges and methods) 3) individual information specific to dynamics of each designer's particular design project experience. Interviewees were selected by purposive sampling based on their level of cross-cultural design experience, the distinction between designers' and users' cultural backgrounds, and the effect of cultural differences on the design process. Ten designers with diverse experiences from different geographical locations in the world were interviewed either face-to-face or by using online communication technologies (Table 1). Although individual designers were interviewed, they often provided examples of designing in a team. Three interviews took place in-person in Hong Kong and Washington DC; six were conducted face to face using synchronous online communication technologies; one used asynchronous

online communication technologies. The interviews lasted one to one and a half hours. Each interview was recorded and transcribed verbatim. The data reduction and analysis were done using the Qualitative Data Analysis Software “NVivo”. The results emerged from three levels of coding: open, axial, and selective coding. Open coding was used to determine concepts by opening up transcriptions and exposing thoughts and meanings contained in the text. Line by line analysis generated over 200 concepts at this stage. In axial coding the aim was reorganizing the data that was opened up. Similar concepts were merged into categories and developed into a tree structure that shows the relationship between concepts and categories. The memos were used for research reflections and interpretations of each concept which helped to recognize implicit meanings and connections. In the third level of selective coding data were transformed into a framework as a result of immersion in data over time. At this stage, the visual model that describes the design process in the cross-cultural context was developed. The model is named as “Culture-Centered Design Process” and its steps and differences from user-centered design process were discussed in detail.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The three levels of coding yielded the theoretical model for the process of culture-centered design.

Figure 2 highlights the major concepts resulting from the analysis of interviews.

The resulting culture-centered design process is composed of two iterative cycles of pre-design and design phases.

Figure 2. Culture-centered design process.

PRE-DESIGN PHASE

The pre-design phase is the very first cyclical step which takes place after the design brief is given to the design team. At this step, the team prepares to design for a different culture and takes several precautions which will ease the process in the future. For example, the cultural difference between designers and users may challenge the communication process during the later stages of the

Designer’s National Culture	Design Field	User’s National Culture	Product Range
India	Industrial Design	China, South Africa	Consumer Goods (i.e. air conditioner, jewelry)
America	Industrial Design	China	Consumer Goods (i.e. rice cooker)
Korea	Clothing Design	Mexico, China America,	Clothing (i.e. menswear, lingerie)
Australia	Industrial Design	Uganda	Consumer Goods (i.e. stove)
Netherlands	Industrial Design & Clothing Design	Turkey	Clothing Accessories (i.e. sportswear hijabs)
England	Industrial Design	China, America	Consumer Electronics (i.e. camcorder)
America	Industrial Design	Africa	Consumer Goods (i.e. carrying cart)
Norway	Industrial Design	China	Consumer Goods and Electronics (i.e. kitchen goods, mobile phones)
Turkey	Industrial Design	Sweden, Netherlands, America	Consumer Goods and Electronics (i.e. healthcare products, printers)
Canada	Communication Design	Rwanda	Website, Logo, Corporate Identity

Table 1. Introduction of the interviewees.

process. Thus, designers should be prepared to understand the accepted norms of behavior and communication prior to meeting users in person. Getting out of the comfort zone and understanding the fact that cross-cultural context may bring extra ambiguity and complexity in the design process should be embraced by designers prior to the project. An Australian designer explains how she felt about designing in Rwanda as follows:

“It can feel that you are going in a very long and random circulus route than maybe what you are comfortable with or normally do”

Background Set-up

At this stage, the design team develops a basic understanding of the culture they will design for through secondary research. Collecting background information about the culture before starting the research in-person is defined as an important step by the interviewees. Indian designer who designs for Chinese culture explains this;

“...It gets you little warmed up with the user whose home you are going to go, -a total stranger- ,when you walk into their home and say I come to spend three hours with you and I want to know everything about your life...”

Strategies used by designers to gather background information include conducting secondary literature research on the culture, gathering statistics and demographics, watching videos and documentaries related to the culture. Designers described this process as usually taking up to a week which helps them to structure the design research and develop their questions which will guide their data collection in that phase.

Developing a “Dos and Don’ts List” as a result of background research prior to moving into design research was defined as a method used to ease future stages:

“I often will draw up a list of dos and don’ts. When you come to somebody’s home, in India for example, if there’s an elderly person at home, be polite to them first before looking, making eye contact to anybody as the way expected in India...similar in China... People don’t like the informality that Americans might sometimes do... So there is a fine balance of informality-formality.”

Presupposition Awareness

The interviews showed that one of the biggest obstacles designers face is ethnocentrism which is perceiving the design problem from their own cultural perspective. This challenge emerges even before the design team starts the design project in the form of presuppositions, stereotypes or prejudices which designers may have about the other culture. Presuppositions are preconceived judgments of a group and its members or evaluation of people simply because they belong to a particular group. These biases of designers do not become visible before the later stages of the design process or worse the designer may never be aware that he/she is approaching the design problem based on these presuppositions. Therefore, it is important that designers become aware of their biases and stay alert and above all not make design decisions based on them. One designer defined a strategy, in making these implicit presuppositions explicit:

“We do something called assumption breaker, which is just a posted exercise. I ask people to dump their ideas on a large white board, everything that is on their mind regarding the project brief, I get the most hilarious and sometimes the great stuff. I was working in India for a client about what the next generation of AC should be in people’s homes who already have two small ACs. So we were talking about people who have enough money to run 2 ACs, which means that they have decent electricity, they must make enough money... Despite the brief and the secondary research my team was still saying things like what do we expect when we go to India, men with swords, dead cows on the street...”

Keeping a log of stereotypes, presuppositions and prejudices about the culture before starting the design project is vital. Role playing exercises among the design team by creating scenarios around this list can also increase awareness and alertness of designers towards these biases.

Finding Access

In a cross-cultural context finding access can be more challenging since designers and users often cannot communicate in a common language. Designers explained the main strategy in finding access into another culture as having a cultural broker. Jezewski & Sotnik (2001) defined culture

broking as “the act of bridging, linking or mediating between groups or persons of differing cultural backgrounds for the purpose of reducing conflict or producing change”. Usually the cultural broker is from one or other of the cultures but could be from a third group capable of acting in both directions. The role covers more than being an interpreter, although this is an important attribute in a cross-cultural situation. In Asian countries the common practice is defined as hiring an agency to act as a cultural broker. Agencies recruit participants for design research by giving incentives in return. It is the agencies’ responsibility to negotiate the communication process between two parties. For more rural cultures such as in Africa, giving incentives to access the culture may not work. Designers emphasized the importance of understanding the leadership roles in the culture and first access those leaders so that they can convince the community to participate in the design research. An Australian designer, designing a stove for rural Uganda, explains the challenges she experienced as follows:

“...when I was working in rural Uganda I needed to organize a workshop for the local villagers. I simply put posters up around the village and told everyone I ran into. On the day of the workshop no-one turned up. I couldn’t understand why. I later found out that the process I went through to mobilize the people was all wrong. I used what I knew worked in my culture. But in this village I needed to inform the council speaker, who would then inform the village elders, who would then mobilize the people.”

In addition, determining the sample size for the design research is an important decision for design teams in finding access into the culture. The interviewees pointed out the importance of maintaining an attitude of diversity for all users, i.e. extreme users as well as secondary users.

DESIGN PHASE

The design phase is composed of four steps, namely; cultural immersion, reflective integration, co-design and implementation, and evaluation. At each step there are different challenges a design team should be aware of and different methods to overcome these challenges. The first step is the cultural

immersion which can be done through in-person user research or remote user research.

Cultural Immersion

Cultural immersion in design refers to designers’ individual exposure to persons or groups markedly different in culture from that of the designers. Interviewees used the term “cultural immersion” together with “environment”; implied is that cultural immersion required physical or remote presence of the designer in the user’s environment.

Cultural immersion in a cross-cultural context can be achieved through in-person research by the design team or remotely by using cultural probes.

The first step to in-person cultural immersion is building **strategic research teams**. Norms of behavior, culturally defined values and roles in a culture should be considered by the design team in developing the cultural immersion strategy. Especially in feminine cultures such as Asian countries where people value relationships and quality of life, it is important to employ female designers in the design research team (Hofstede, 1991). A Norwegian designer explains how they structured research teams in a project in China: *“...We were very strategic when it comes to the (research) groups; if there was a man in the group we ensured that there are two women, especially if the man was a foreigner... People don’t want to let three foreign guys in their flat which I can understand.”*

Building relationship with the other culture is another important aspect of in-person design research. Users participating in the design research will become more open and cooperative when the design team shows interest in them regardless of design goals.

Interviewees used the terms “people’s person”, “approachable”, “friendly”, “respectful” to describe how they should be reaching out to individuals during design research. Making compliments and using phrases like “I hear you”, “I understand you” to encourage the participant users to be more open is defined as helpful. In building a relationship with the user group, design teams should also focus on **role negotiation**. This concept refers to redefining the perception of the designer as the expert and the

users as the research subjects. Both the design team and users should embrace each other as co-partners. Also learning the basic words of the host culture's **language** is defined as a positive factor in building relationship with the users:

"...learning the local language was a way, people are always impressed with you, just as a traveler, but as a designer, it helps bridge barriers of understanding if you attempt to learn the language, so I'd say that's another skill set or tool that worked to access..."

Interviewees defined cultural immersion methods as having direct contact with users in their real life setting to empathize with users and get insights into their needs, limitations and aspirations.

The very first method is **non-participant observation** where the design team is quiet, watching and shadowing users and trying to understand and experience their way of life, behaviors and environment. After non-participant observation and passive experience, design teams employed **participant observation** where they actively experience and feel users' life by imitating them:

"...I went with them to where they extracted the plants, they ultimately were weaving with, and I involved myself in that experience with them, to try to get in their shoes and understand, how far the distance it is they had to travel, and sort of the whole complexity of their reality that is not my reality."

Interview as a cultural immersion method is described as informal and friendly talks and discussions. Being quiet, letting the user talk and using encouraging probes to trigger stories are the actions that should be taken by the design teams. Interviewees described the use of **visual cultural probes** in addition to supportive and encouraging manners to have the users talk during interviews. One interviewee described that users were sent disposable cameras and asked to document their daily activities via photographs. Then, these cameras were sent back and the design team analyzed photos to develop the interview questions. When the design team met with users for the interview, they used photos to ask the questions. This process not only triggers stories but also excites users and gives them an active role in the research process. In addition, collecting these images before meeting the user

group in-person helps to break some of the presuppositions designers may have about the culture or to validate the facts about the users' environment:

"...I ask them (users) to talk about these pictures. That works like magic, these people haven't seen the pictures they took, everyone wants to see the pictures, if I take pictures I want to see what they look like. So, they just get involved with these pictures and these pictures trigger stories that they wouldn't have told me otherwise, It is amazing the information that I get out of that, of course I have a discussion guide and I stir in questions out of that guide, but I often show those pictures and ask is there anything here that can help you to answer..."

In classical ethnography methods of observation and interviews, users have passive roles, involving them in the research process and moving them away from the passive role by engaging them in the process creates fruitful results. In this way, users own the project, and the perception of the design team as the expert coming into their house and questioning them is eased.

Language --both verbal and non-verbal-- was defined as the major barrier for cultural immersion in cross-cultural design contexts. To overcome this challenge design teams hire interpreters when they reach out to individuals for interview or observation sessions. However, interviewees all agreed that they miss a lot of contextual information as well as a link with the other culture when they have to use interpreters:

"...Everything is just a repetition of what they (translator) said five minutes ago, which I don't believe. So we miss out on a lot of information."

The changes in body language from culture to culture were also defined as an obstacle in communication.

The challenges designers face forced them to develop different strategies than only relying on the interpreters. Interviewees described that they became better observers due to limited verbal communication and they use visual tools, such as images, and visual cultural probes in design research. Involving users in the research with a more active role and developing visuals dictionaries were defined as helpful tools when communication in common language is not possible.

Time is another major barrier in the cross-cultural design processes. There may be multiple unexpected

factors that can delay the cultural immersion stage as well as the whole design process; therefore cross-cultural design contexts call for flexibility in time. Interviewees explained that they miss a lot of information by “fast fashion style”, quick design projects. There was common desire among interviewees for longer design processes, especially in the cultural immersion phase. Understanding a design problem in the context of another culture not only requires understanding the problem itself but also the people and their way of life. Additionally, biases and assumptions designers may hold towards the culture can be recognized over time. The more time a designer spends with the other culture, the more he/she sees the context of the design problem from the other cultures perspectives without judgments:

“...I think it is better to have a longer amount of time if you can because there are things that I think shifted in my mind from when I first landed to when I was ready to depart, even in the way I review it now that I’m removed from it immediately.”

Safety is a concern when designers conduct design research in a different culture, especially in less-developed countries, in neighborhoods where crimes rates are high:

“...In South Africa my client was so freaked, they were South Africans and they said listen ‘No you just stay in your hotel; we will pick you up and drop you back every day, you don’t venture anywhere by yourself.’ Johannesburg is a very dangerous place. So I never went to Johannesburg downtown because of the horror stories I heard there.”

Extreme weather conditions and regional diseases were defined as safety issues. One of the interviewees told the story of how she got malaria in Africa while she was conducting design research.

Cost is one other challenge in cross-cultural design contexts especially when design teams travel to the other culture. Transportation and accommodation of the design team, hiring recruitment agencies, interpreters, and incentives given to the users add to the cost of the design project. The extended schedules can also increase the cost of cross-cultural design processes.

Remote user research in cultural immersion is employed when design teams do not have the financial resources, time and infrastructure to

relocate. The main method employed in remote user research is cultural probes. They provide a way of gathering information about people and their activities which allows users to self-report through diaries (Gaver, Dunne & Pacenti, 1999). Cultural probe kits usually include a diary, pens, sticky notes, recording devices, camera, etc. Users are usually given a set of materials and guidelines about what and how to record through a specific period of time. When conducting remote research through cultural probes in another culture there are several challenges in developing the toolkit as well as in running the process, such as data safety, flexibility, bureaucracy, and communication.

Instead of adopting existing toolkits, developing the toolkit based on the context where it will be used is a vital step if data collection is done remotely in the other culture. An interviewee described an example of how different cultural contexts require different toolkits. In this example the components of the toolkit were developed to ensure the **security of the data** collected. The toolkit was developed for a design project in South African low income communities where crime rates are high. Instead of using the standard disposable cameras which might be stolen, the design team decided to include Polaroid cameras which would not be worthy of stealing since its films are expensive and its resale is not common. Different from disposable cameras, Polaroid cameras allowed users to immediately see the photos they took and share them with their community and talk about them. The design team also took precautions to secure the safety of the data --the photo taken by the participants--:

“...The problem then was what if the pictures get spoiled? So then we decided let’s get something that is a metallic box, maybe something like chocolates or cookies in it. And we’ll give them the box and tell them to consume the cookies and chocolates, and then clean the box, and then start using the camera and save the pictures. So this way the pictures will be safe in a nice box. So we did that. And the users were delighted. Of course with this expensive box of biscuits that they don’t even buy once a year, they were very happy.”

In remote cultural immersion, the design team needs to consider the **bureaucratic procedures** of sending the cultural probe materials. One interviewee

explained how the design project was affected by the delay in sending cultural probe kits due to the bureaucracy in Indian customs. **Being flexible** towards unexpected delays such as the customs example is an important asset a design team should have in cross-cultural contexts. Remote user research in another culture requires flexibility in time as well as being flexible in changing the structure of data collection.

Communication is a challenge in remote immersion contexts. Design teams will need a cultural broker who will communicate between the two cultures and conduct the cultural probe exercises and send the kits and results back. Design teams need to keep in mind that the communication channels such as Internet may not be decent. Guidelines provided in the toolkit are the only means design teams communicate with users. Therefore, instructions should be very clear and easy to understand. The guidelines may also require translation into the user groups' language. Pilot testing the toolkit before sending it out helps to overcome any communication problems that may occur due to not very clearly-written instructions.

Reflective Integration

Reflective photo and video journaling, role playing, behavioral personas, affinity diagrams, and mind maps were reported as useful methods to integrate research results from cultural immersion. Redefining the problem statement based on design research results requires **systems thinking**. It refers to conceptual thinking about the cultural context surrounding the design problem, understanding roles, actors, behaviors and context around it. One of the examples given by an interviewee was about the use of washing machines in India. In this example there were the roles of user and owner, which the interviewee explained as typical in a higher income household in India. The user was the maid in the household and the owner was the mother of the household. The maid actually washed clothing in the washing machine while the owner displayed it. The maid was concerned with the functionality of the washing machine while the owner was concerned with the prestige of owning that particular washing machine. One context was simple and easy to use washing machines and the other context was the

elegant look. And, the overall cultural context surrounding the washing machine was the clothing experience in India, the long Saris and their delicate materials. Therefore, the washing machine needs to be able to wash a meters long Sari without getting stuck, it should be simple enough to be used by a maid and elegant looking for the owner to enhance her self-image.

To develop systems thinking ability designers need to see the problem beyond the context of use, understand the culture from multiple perspectives which means not only see them through the lens of judgments, biases, and stereotypes but see the actual reality of the users.

However, one challenge in synthesizing design research results to create meaning is the **perceptual filter** of the design team. Reality is a very fluid concept and what someone perceives as real goes through his/her perceptual filter; the filter of their belief system, judgments, prejudices and stereotypes. A Dutch designer developing sportswear veils for Muslim immigrants explains how her perceptual filter worked in developing her problem statement:

"...the image of covering or veiling was then of suppressed women walking ten meters behind her husband living a very isolated life and being a fundamentalist... now we have migrants living in our country and the image we had of the first generation is not up to date anymore.... now these women are demanding a place in the work place... they've become lawyers and they have become teachers."

It is challenging to understand and redefine the design problem based on the reality of the user group, because designers often feel responsible for improving lives of people bringing their efficiencies into the other culture:

"...One of the hardest things to erase is cultural biases though. It's hard not to try to change the way others do things just because you might think that your way is more logical or efficient. Often there are reasons for their way of doing things that perhaps you don't understand."

Co-design and Implementation

Involving users in the development of product ideas was a common practice among interviewees. Users

were involved in the idea generation process with simply sketching and discussing their ideas, low-tech prototyping, developing inspirational collages, and testing and critiquing early prototypes. This process was defined as helpful in overcoming the challenges of 1. cultural and designerly bias in aesthetic design choices, 2. application of cultural human factors. Designers referenced **aesthetic** and appearance in design such as forms, colors and textures as factors that need to be considered in a cross-cultural context. Visual aspects of design are considered as universal, hardwired and evolutionarily driven since responses to visual stimuli are subconsciously acquired. Gestalt principles discuss how our brains group elements into a unified whole to aid in processing of visual information. The golden ratio or the divine proportion in art and design also addresses the hardwired response to visceral characteristics. However, in a cross-cultural design process the cultural context, date, time, place as well as values and ideals of a society can affect the aesthetic perceptions (DeLong, 1998). Aesthetics or what is regarded as beautiful and valued by a culture and ideals of beauty are sensitive to cultural differences. There was significant emphasis especially on preference of colors among interviewees; Western designers experiencing design for Eastern user groups stated how colorful it is in designing for Eastern markets. In Chinese and Indian cultures who have rich symbolic contexts surrounding color, understanding and reflecting upon this context in design is a necessity. The Korean home appliances company LG has been investing in research to design for the Indian market. The company developed the "Stars of India" line of household appliances. Dark red color and floral patterns were incorporated in the design of washing machines and red color is associated with purity in Indian culture. Designers interviewed stated their struggle between their own designerly aesthetic preferences versus the aesthetic expectations of that culture:

"...when working on the rice cooker and the induction cookers, when we were sketching out the induction cookers they wanted to put all these flowery graphics on the cookers. To us it just looks really ugly, and we wanted to make it plain and with nice curves, they wanted it to look like it was from 90s very floral, we didn't like but again it is not for us."

Human factors can vary among cultures both at physical, cognitive and emotional levels and **cultural human factors** deal with these differences. At the physical level, anthropometrics which are related to measurement of the human body can vary among cultures. Especially, in the specific field of clothing design it becomes a big concern. The body structure and proportion of individuals change from culture to culture and this needs to be considered in the design of clothing:

"... the black lady, has very pronounced hips. And I cut the pattern for her, an A-line skirt, it didn't fit. I don't know how to fix it. And I was so worried because it doesn't fit. And I asked another pattern maker, how do you fix the problem? And he's, 'oh just rotate the skirt.' What do you mean, rotate the skirt?... So I immediately rotate when I do the fitting."

Cultural human factors is also related to the context that surrounds design problem residing in cultural differences such as values, beliefs and knowledge or technology. The example below --a design process on designing veils for Muslim women to be worn during sports activities-- shows how human factors can be affected by cultural values. According to the religious belief the veil needs to cover women's hair and neck, therefore the designer deals with issues of securing the veil during high impact physical activities, and finding materials that don't shine through without impacting the hearing ability.

"...I chose a stretchable material that fits most women snug around the face. Some are adjustable with Velcro, it's not supposed to shine through so the material needs to be thick enough. It needs to be safe, so on one model we have Velcro, when you pull it rips off so you don't get stuck. One of the first prototypes that I made for the tennis model was that of a more firm piece of material. When the women were wearing it they said that it causes noise. Prior to production I changed it to a more flexible material."

Evaluation

At the evaluation stage design solutions that have been developed should be considered from two perspectives; local competition and possible unintended consequences of the solutions.

As markets outside the main stream Western consumption culture are expanding, local design driven companies are emerging. Therefore, any culture-centered design process requires understanding of the **local competition** related to the specific product. Especially for large Western corporations local competition in another culture can be very challenging. Smaller local companies are nimble and flexible enough to respond to any competition and hold the advantage of understating the culture.

On the other hand, cross-cultural contexts can provide opportunities to design creative solutions. Because of the cultural difference the design teams do not take things for granted and they are likely to catch the little details related to the design problem:

“...I think I am usually better designing for another culture than I am for my own culture because when I do research in my own culture, I take everything for granted.”

Cross-cultural contexts in design may create some **unintended consequences**; outcomes that are not intended by a purposeful action. According to unintended consequences theory (Merton, 1936), an intervention in a complex system always creates unanticipated outcomes. Design in a cross-cultural context can also be considered as an intervention in the other cultural system. Thus, it is important for the companies to follow up on the influence of their product on the culture for further development of the products. One of the interviewees described how they purposefully designed the product in a modular structure. In this way, they would be able to change the product in the future easily as they gather feedback about it in the market.

CONCLUSION

This study employed grounded theory methodology to shed light on how we can design for other cultures, the challenges of this process and its methods. In conclusion, further possible researches are discussed and the research questions that guided this study are responded;

CHALLENGES OF DESIGNING FOR OTHER CULTURES

The results of this study showed that cultural differences between designer and user offer some

challenges in different phases of the design process; some challenges may exist and affect the whole process. Gaining access into the culture is the first challenge design teams often face in cross-cultural design contexts. Time is a challenge that affects all steps of culture-centered design processes. Designers acknowledge that building relationships with the user and creating empathy requires careful time management. Interviewees articulated their aspiration for longer time especially in the cultural immersion step.

Language is another challenge that mostly effects cultural immersion as well as co-design steps. Not being able to communicate in a common language and therefore using interpreters causes missing contextual information.

Resistance from the other culture in contributing to the design research or co-design is one of the major obstacles.

Designers' implicit biases towards the users' culture may result in wrong insights for product development.

Designing for other cultures is also costly since it requires transportation of the team and accommodation. Hiring recruitment agencies and incentives given to users for participation in the design research are other possible costs.

METHODS FOR OVERCOMING THE CHALLENGES OF DESIGNING FOR OTHER CULTURES

Design teams need to understand the social hierarchy and gender roles within the users' culture to gain access into their culture and to design for them. At this stage, finding a cultural broker who will negotiate communication between both parties is important.

Any stereotypes that a designer may have about the users' culture and that create a cultural bias should be acknowledged and dealt with prior to research. Keeping a log of any assumptions, stereotypes and prejudices can help to increase a design teams' awareness about their biases.

Developing basic knowledge about the other culture such as their norms, values and beliefs, and creating a Do's and Don'ts List can be helpful.

Communication challenges can be overcome by developing visual dictionaries, using interpreters, and emphasizing visual cultural probes. Observation

is the strongest data collection tool designers can lean on where communication is limited. Cost challenges can be minimized by employing remote research methods in cultural immersion. Resistance of users in contributing to design research can be avoided by developing empathy, building relationships and keeping the awareness of cultural biases alive, giving users more active roles in data collection through camera ethnographies to encourage their participation.

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CULTURE-CENTERED DESIGN AND GENERIC USER-CENTERED DESIGN

The very early phase of the cross-cultural design process involves negotiation (Goncu-Berk, DeLong & LaBat, 2010), which is a pre-design phase where the design teams position themselves in the cultural context to overcome challenges of access and cultural bias. The pre-design phase is the main difference between the generic user centered design process and culture-centered design process. Involvement in the pre-design phase grounds the design process and eases future challenges and saves time. In addition, it is important to get the design team out of their comfort zones. Although the design phase does not show much difference in terms of the steps taken, there are challenges unique to cross-cultural contexts.

In addition to laying out dynamics of the culture-centered design process, this research is an example for application of grounded theory methodology which offers a method to abstract from practical processes and from the field experiences. For future research, this study may pave the way to other similar applications in the Design field. The results of this study can be applied to different cultural contexts other than the national level. The definition of culture can be widened to any group of people experiencing a set of knowledge built over time. New design research methods and ideation methods that respond to challenges of cultural difference between design teams and users can be developed. Design research techniques such as focus groups or integration techniques such as personas can be evaluated for their applicability in different cultural contexts.

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